

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Prevention/Preventive chemotherapies

Section

4.2.5 Post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PDMC). In *WHO Guidelines for malaria*, 3 June 2022.

Title

AMSTAR2 review of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention in children admitted with severe anaemia in malaria-endemic settings in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis

Authors

Julie R Gutman, Julie I Thwing

Contact

gmpfeedback@who.int

This report was reviewed by the Guideline Development Group on Malaria Chemoprevention, convened by the World Health Organization Global Malaria Programme to support the development of recommendations included in the *WHO Guidelines for malaria*. It is being made publicly available for transparency purposes and information, in accordance with the *WHO handbook for guideline development, 2nd edition (2014)*.

The designations employed and the presentation of the material in this publication do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of WHO concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. Dotted and dashed lines on maps represent approximate border lines for which there may not yet be full agreement.

The mention of specific companies or of certain manufacturers' products does not imply that they are endorsed or recommended by WHO in preference to others of a similar nature that are not mentioned. Errors and omissions excepted, the names of proprietary products are distinguished by initial capital letters.

All reasonable precautions have been taken by WHO to verify the information contained in this publication. However, the published material is being distributed without warranty of any kind, either expressed or implied. The responsibility for the interpretation and use of the material lies with the reader. In no event shall WHO be liable for damages arising from its use.

The named authors alone are responsible for the views expressed in this document.

The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

AMSTAR2¹ Review of Post-discharge Malaria Chemoprevention in Children Admitted with Severe Anaemia in Malaria-Endemic Settings in Africa: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Kamija S. Phiri, MD, PhD; Carole Khairallah, MSc; Titus K Kwambai, MD, PhD; Kalifa Bojang, MD, PhD; Aggrey Dhabangi, MD, PhD; Robert Opoka, MD, PhD; Richard Idro, MD, PhD; Kasia Stepniewska, PhD; Bjarne Robberstad, PhD; Brian Greenwood, MD; Feiko O ter Kuile, MD, PhD

AMSTAR2 review completed by Julie R Gutman, MD MSc and Julie I Thwing, MD

Kamija et al. completed a systematic review assessing the efficacy of monthly post-discharge chemoprevention for malaria on mortality, all-cause readmissions, severe malaria and severe anemia readmissions as determined by randomized controlled clinical trials.

While the described search is adequate, the outcome of the search presented in Figure 1 (PRISMA flow diagram) appears to include only articles identified in PubMed, as a search of other databases identified substantially more articles. From the databases where we re-reviewed the list of articles, it does not appear that this resulted in any eligible studies being excluded, however, we have not yet reviewed the entire list from EMBASE to verify this.

The systematic review identified three double-blind placebo-controlled trials, involving 3,663 children with severe anaemia. The regimens included monthly sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) until the end of the malaria transmission season (average: 3.1 doses per child) (N=1,200, the Gambia), monthly artemether-lumefantrine (AL) given at 4 and 8 weeks post-discharge (N=1,414, Malawi), and monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine given at the start of the 3rd, 7th, and 10th week post-discharge (N=1,049, Uganda and Kenya).

They found that PMC was associated with:

- 77% (95% CI 30-92) reduction in mortality during the intervention period (p=0.01, I²=0%)
- 58% (48-66) reduction in all-cause readmissions (p<0.001, I²=87%)
- 68% (54-78) reduction in readmissions due to severe malaria (p<0.001, I²=93%)
- 62% (44-74) reduction in readmissions due to severe anaemia (p<0.001, I²=69%)
- 24% (17-31) reduction in non-severe all-cause sick-child clinic visits (p<0.001, I²=10%)
- 57% (50-64) reduction in uncomplicated clinical malaria (p<0.001, I²=71%)

The concluded that there was a substantial reduction in all outcomes, however, this was restricted to the intervention period and not sustained after protective drug levels had waned.

We found the review to be of overall good quality, however the questions associated with the search strategy leave open the possibility that eligible articles could have been missed.

¹Shea BJ, Reeves BC, Wells G, Thuku M, Hamel C, Moran J, Moher D, Tugwell P, Welch V, Kristjansson E, Henry DA. AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both. *BMJ*. 2017 Sep 21;358:j4008.

AMSTAR2 Checklist

1. Did the research questions and inclusion criteria for the review include the components of PICO?
All components of the PICO question were included
2. Did the report of the review contain an explicit statement that the review methods were established prior to the conduct of the review and did the report justify any significant deviations from the protocol?
No. This was not explicitly stated in the manuscript. A search on PROSPERO identified the review protocol which was registered on Feb 4, 2022.
Kamija Phiri, Carole Khairallah. Malaria chemoprevention for the post-discharge management of severe anaemia in children: an individual participant data meta-analysis (PDMC-IPD). PROSPERO 2022 CRD42022308791 Available from: https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?ID=CRD42022308791
3. Did the review authors explain their selection of the study designs for inclusion in the review?
No explanation was provided for inclusion of only RCTs in the manuscript. We reached out to the authors and asked for this information; the authors provided the following:
This specific review by Phiri et al, 2022, was aimed at assessing the efficacy and safety of PDMC relative to the standard of care using the highest quality design; i.e. RCTs. Other aspects such as the burden and contextual factors involving observational studies were addressed in two other reviews (see below).
This review was not designed to assess the burden of post-discharge morbidity and mortality, which was assessed as part of another review (Kwambai TK, Mori AT, Nevitt S, Anna Maria van Eijk AM, Samuels AM, Robberstad B, Phiri KS, ter Kuile FO, 2022. Post-discharge morbidity and mortality in children admitted with severe anaemia and/or other health-conditions in malaria-endemic settings in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Under review by Lancet CAH. This review was also not designed to assess contextual factors of PDMC, which is also addressed in another review (Lange S, Nkosi-Gondwe T, Svege S, 2022. Adherence, acceptability and feasibility of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PDMC): a systematic review. for WHO.)
4. Did the review authors use a comprehensive literature search strategy?
Yes, they searched PubMed, SCOPUS, EMBASE, Web of Science, Cochrane CENTRAL and the WHO's clinical trial registry from inception to January 04, 2022. In addition, other relevant studies were identified by scanning reference lists of all identified articles without language restrictions.
5. Did the review authors perform study selection in duplicate? Yes
6. Did the review authors perform data extraction in duplicate? Yes
7. Did the review authors provide a list of excluded studies and justify the exclusions?
Not in the manuscript. They note that 10 full texts were reviewed, and 7 were excluded, 5 were not RCTs (but references/ titles not provided) and 2 did not use monthly prophylaxis. We reached out to the authors and asked for this information; it is provided in **Appendix 1** and is adequate.

8. Did the review authors describe the included studies in adequate detail? Yes
9. Did the review authors use a satisfactory technique for assessing the risk of bias (RoB) in individual studies that were included in the review?
Yes, they used ROB2, and had only RCTs.
10. Did the review authors report on the sources of funding for the studies included in the review?
Not in the manuscript. We reached out to the authors and asked for this information; the authors provided the following:
- *Bojang et al, 2010: "The study received financial support from the Gates malaria partnership. The funder had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript."*
 - *Phiri et al, 2012: "The Netherlands African Partnership for Capacity Development and Clinical Interventions Against Poverty Related Diseases (NACCAP), the UBS-Optimus Foundation, and the Gates Malaria Partnership." "The sponsors of the study had no role in the study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or writing of the report"*
 - *Kwambai et al, 2020: "(Funded by the Research Council of Norway and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention)" "The funders had no role in the design or execution of the trial, the analysis or interpretation of the data, or the decision to submit the manuscript for publication"*
11. If meta-analysis was performed did the review authors use appropriate methods for statistical combination of results?
Only RCTs were included; methods were appropriate.
12. If meta-analysis was performed, did the review authors assess the potential impact of RoB in individual studies on the results of the meta-analysis or other evidence synthesis?
Only low ROB studies were included.
13. Did the review authors account for RoB in individual studies when interpreting/ discussing the results of the review?
Only low ROB studies were included.
14. Did the review authors provide a satisfactory explanation for, and discussion of, any heterogeneity observed in the results of the review?
There were too few studies to stratify/ assess heterogeneity.
15. If they performed quantitative synthesis did the review authors carry out an adequate investigation of publication bias (small study bias) and discuss its likely impact on the results of the review?
Too few studies.
16. Did the review authors report any potential sources of conflict of interest, including any funding they received for conducting the review?
Yes. The authors report no COI.

Additional points:

Assessment of adequacy of the search.

The search terms used by the review authors in PubMed were:

(child OR childhood OR infant OR pediatric OR paediatric) AND (malaria OR plasmodium) AND (“severe anaemia” OR “severe anemia” OR transfusion) AND (recurrence OR discharge OR postdischarge OR post-discharge)

We repeated the search using these search terms, with outcome as detailed below and in Figure 1.

PubMed: Using these same search terms, restricted to studies prior to Jan 2, 2022, we found 75 articles in PubMed. Restricting to RCTs reduces this number to 14 (see list below); these were reviewed and no additional articles which should have been included were identified (3 included articles in bold).

WHO clinical trial registry: Searching the WHO clinical trial registry for studies of “malaria” and “anemia” in children identified 3 articles, 2 which were already included and one which assessed iron supplementation for severe anemia and was not the correct intervention.

SCOPUS: Searching SCOPUS identified 803 articles; restricting this to “articles” provided 363; these were reviewed and no additional relevant publication were identified.

EMBASE: EMBASE was “searched” using Scopus, not full database as CDC does not have access; this yielded 590- these are all duplicates of articles found in SCOPUS

Web of Science: Not searched, CDC does not have access.

Cochrane CENTRAL: Searching Cochrane CENTRAL identified 59 articles; a review of this list did not identify any additional articles which should have been included.

Figure 1. PRISMA DIAGRAM Numbers of records identified as eligible via search strategy

 3 records for 3 trials found for: severe anemia AND malaria [\[What is this?\]](#)
[Display synonyms](#)

Recruitment status	Prospective Registration	Main ID	Public Title	Date of Registration
Not recruiting	Yes	NCT02721420	Delivery of Malaria Chemoprevention in the Post-discharge Management of Children With Severe Anaemia in Malawi	2016-02-13
Not recruiting	Yes	NCT02671175	Post-discharge Malaria Chemoprevention(PMC) Study	2016-01-28
Not recruiting	No	NCT00497471	RCT Iron Supplementation and Malaria Chemoprophylaxis for Prevention of Severe Anemia and Malaria in Tanzanian Infants	2007-07-05

PubMed RCTs

- Intermittent preventive therapy for malaria with monthly artemether-lumefantrine for the post-discharge management of severe anaemia in children aged 4-59 months in southern Malawi: a multicentre, randomised, placebo-controlled trial.** Phiri K, Esan M, van Hensbroek MB, Khairallah C, Faragher B, ter Kuile FO. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2012 Mar;**12**(3):191-200. doi: 10.1016/S1473-3099(11)70320-6. Epub 2011 Dec 13. (INCLUDED)
- Prevention of the recurrence of anaemia in Gambian children following discharge from hospital.** Bojang KA, Milligan PJ, Conway DJ, Sisay-Joof F, Jallow M, Nwakanma DC, Abubakr I, Njie F, Greenwood B. *PLoS One.* 2010 Jun 21;**5**(6):e11227. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0011227. (INCLUDED)
- Malaria Chemoprevention in the Postdischarge Management of Severe Anemia.** Kwambai TK, Dhabangi A, Idro R, Opoka R, Watson V, Kariuki S, Kuya NA, Onyango ED, Otieno K, Samuels AM, Desai MR, Boele van Hensbroek M, Wang D, John CC, Robberstad B, Phiri KS, Ter Kuile FO. *N Engl J Med.* 2020 Dec 3;**383**(23):2242-2254. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2002820. (INCLUDED)
- Vitamin A supplementation and other predictors of anemia among children from Dar Es Salaam, Tanzania. Villamor E, et al. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2000 May;**62**(5):590-7. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.2000.62.590.
- Management of severe malarial anaemia in Gambian children. Bojang KA, et al. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg.* 1997 Sep-Oct;**91**(5):557-61. doi: 10.1016/s0035-9203(97)90025-0. -> *treatment with blood transfusion or oral iron, no antimalarials*
- Influence of lime juice on the severity of sickle cell anemia. Adegoke SA, et al. *J Altern Complement Med.* 2013;**19**(6):588-92. doi: 10.1089/acm.2012.0567.
- Increasing evidence-based interventions in patients with acute infections in a resource-limited setting: a before-and-after feasibility trial in Gitwe, Rwanda. Urayeneza O, et al; Sepsis in Resource-Limited Nations Workgroup of the Surviving Sepsis Campaign. *Intensive Care Med.* 2018 Sep;**44**(9):1436-1446. doi: 10.1007/s00134-018-5266-x.
- Post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PMC) in Malawi: caregivers' acceptance and preferences with regard to delivery methods. Svege S, et al. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2018;**18**(1):544. doi: 10.1186/s12913-018-3327-z.

9. Delivery strategies for malaria chemoprevention with monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperazine for the post-discharge management of severe anaemia in children aged less than 5 years old in Malawi: a protocol for a cluster randomized trial. Gondwe T, et al. *BMC Pediatr.* 2018;18(1):238. doi: 10.1186/s12887-018-1199-3.
10. Introducing post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PMC) for management of severe anemia in Malawian children: a qualitative study of community health workers' perceptions and motivation. Nkosi-Gondwe T, et al. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2018 Dec 19;18(1):984. doi: 10.1186/s12913-018-3791-5.
11. Chloroquine Versus Dihydroartemisinin-Piperazine With Standard High-dose Primaquine Given Either for 7 Days or 14 Days in Plasmodium vivax Malaria. Chu CS, Phyo AP, Turner C, Win HH, Poe NP, Yotyingaphiram W, Thinraow S, Wilairisak P, Raksapraidee R, Carrara VI, Paw MK, Wiladphaingern J, Proux S, Banccone G, Sriprawat K, Lee SJ, Jeeyapant A, Watson J, Tarning J, Imwong M, Nosten F, White NJ. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2019 Apr 8;68(8):1311-1319. doi: 10.1093/cid/ciy735.
12. Immediate Transfusion in African Children with Uncomplicated Severe Anemia. Maitland K, Kiguli S, Olupot-Olupot P, Engoru C, Mallewa M, Saramago Goncalves P, Opoka RO, Mpoya A, Alaroker F, Nteziyaremye J, Chagaluka G, Kennedy N, Nabawanuka E, Nakuya M, Namayanja C, Uyoga S, Kyeyune Byabazaire D, M'baya B, Wabwire B, Frost G, Bates I, Evans JA, Williams TN, George EC, Gibb DM, Walker AS; TRACT Group. *N Engl J Med.* 2019 Aug 1;381(5):407-419. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1900105.
13. Transfusion Volume for Children with Severe Anemia in Africa. Maitland K, Olupot-Olupot P, Kiguli S, Chagaluka G, Alaroker F, Opoka RO, Mpoya A, Engoru C, Nteziyaremye J, Mallewa M, Kennedy N, Nakuya M, Namayanja C, Kayaga J, Uyoga S, Kyeyune Byabazaire D, M'baya B, Wabwire B, Frost G, Bates I, Evans JA, Williams TN, Saramago Goncalves P, George EC, Gibb DM, Walker AS; TRACT Group. *N Engl J Med.* 2019 Aug 1;381(5):420-431. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1900100.
14. Adherence to community versus facility-based delivery of monthly malaria chemoprevention with dihydroartemisinin-piperazine for the post-discharge management of severe anemia in Malawian children: A cluster randomized trial. Nkosi-Gondwe T, Robberstad B, Mukaka M, Idro R, Opoka RO, Banda S, Kühl MJ, O Ter Kuile F, Blomberg B, Phiri KS. *PLoS One.* 2021 Sep 10;16(9):e0255769. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0255769. eCollection 2021.

Appendix 1. Reasons for exclusion of studies reviewed at the full text stage provided by the authors

REASONS FOR EXCLUSION OF 7 STUDIES

1 DELIVERY MECHANISM TRIAL (N=1)

1. Nkosi-Gondwe T, Robberstad B, Mukaka M, Idro R, Opoka RO, Banda S, Kuhl MJ, F OTK, Blomberg B, Phiri KS, 2021. Adherence to community versus facility-based delivery of monthly malaria chemoprevention with dihydroartemisinin-piperazine for the post-discharge management of severe anemia in Malawian children: A cluster randomized trial. *PLoS One* 16: e0255769.

Reason for exclusion: This was a delivery mechanism trial with adherence as the primary outcome. All arms received PDMC. There was no control arm for standard of care or placebo so efficacy of the intervention on clinical outcomes not assessed.

2 OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES (ACCEPTABILITY, FEASIBILITY) (N=2)

2. Nkosi-Gondwe T, Robberstad B, Blomberg B, Phiri KS, Lange S, 2018. Introducing post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PMC) for management of severe anemia in Malawian children: a qualitative study of community health workers' perceptions and motivation. *BMC Health Serv Res* 18: 984.

Reason for exclusion: Acceptability-feasibility study, not a RCT

3. Svege S, Kaunda B, Robberstad B, Nkosi-Gondwe T, Phiri KS, Lange S, 2018. Post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PMC) in Malawi: caregivers' acceptance and preferences with regard to delivery methods. *BMC Health Serv Res* 18: 544.

Reason for exclusion: Acceptability-feasibility study, not a RCT

3 TRIAL PROTOCOLS (N=2)

4. Gondwe T, Robberstad B, Mukaka M, Lange S, Blomberg B, Phiri KS, 2018. Delivery strategies for malaria chemoprevention with monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperazine for the post-discharge management of severe anaemia in children aged less than 5 years old in Malawi: a protocol for a cluster randomized trial. *BMC Pediatrics* 18: 8.

Reason for exclusion: publication of study protocol

5. Kwambai TK, Dhabangi A, Idro R, Opoka R, Kariuki S, Samuels AM, Desai M, van Hensbroek MB, John CC, Robberstad B, Wang D, Phiri K, Ter Kuile FO, 2018. Malaria chemoprevention with monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperazine for the post-discharge management of severe anaemia in children aged less than 5 years in Uganda and Kenya: study protocol for a multi-centre, two-arm, randomised, placebo-controlled, superiority trial. *Trials* 19: 610.

Reason for exclusion: publication of study protocol

4 DAILY OR WEEKLY PROPHYLAXIS INSTEAD OF MONTHLY IPT (N=2)

6. Maitland K, Olupot-Olupot P, Kiguli S, Chagaluka G, Alaroker F, Opoka RO, Mpoya A, Walsh K, Engoru C, Nteziyaremye J, Mallewa M, Kennedy N, Nakuya M, Namayanja C, Kayaga J, Nabawanuka E, Sennyondo T, Aromut D, Kumwenda F, Musika CW, Thomason MJ, Bates I,

von Hensbroek MB, Evans JA, Uyoga S, Williams TN, Frost G, George EC, Gibb DM, Walker AS, group Tt, 2019. Co-trimoxazole or multivitamin multimineral supplement for post-discharge outcomes after severe anaemia in African children: a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet Glob Health* 7: e1435-e1447.

Reason for exclusion: post-discharge RCT with daily cotrimoxazole as the intervention (thus not intermittent preventive treatment / monthly prophylaxis)

7. Bojang KA, Palmer A, Boele van Hensbroek M, Banya WA, Greenwood BM, 1997. Management of severe malarial anaemia in Gambian children. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg* 91: 557-61.

Reason for exclusion: Post-discharge RCT with weekly Maloprim as the intervention (thus not intermittent preventive treatment / monthly prophylaxis)

5 INCLUDED IN THE ANALYSIS (N=3)

8. Bojang KA, Milligan PJ, Conway DJ, Sisay-Joof F, Jallow M, Nwakanma DC, Abubakr I, Njie F, Greenwood B, 2010. Prevention of the recurrence of anaemia in Gambian children following discharge from hospital. *PLoS One* 5: e11227.
9. Phiri K, Esan M, van Hensbroek MB, Khairallah C, Faragher B, ter Kuile FO, 2012. Intermittent preventive therapy for malaria with monthly artemether-lumefantrine for the post-discharge management of severe anaemia in children aged 4-59 months in southern Malawi: a multicentre, randomised, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet Infect Dis* 12: 191-200.
10. Kwambai TK, Dhabangi A, Idro R, Opoka R, Watson V, Kariuki S, Kuya NA, Onyango ED, Otieno K, Samuels AM, Desai MR, Boele van Hensbroek M, Wang D, John CC, Robberstad B, Phiri KS, Ter Kuile FO, 2020. Malaria Chemoprevention in the Postdischarge Management of Severe Anemia. *N Engl J Med* 383: 2242-2254.

Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.